

EVALUATION OF BOTANICALS ON MAJOR INSECT PESTS OF OKRA

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Abstract:

The present studies entitled, "Evaluation of botanicals on major insect pests of okra" was carried out with a view to manage the major pests on okra with the use of botanicals. The experiment was carried out on the research field of Dr. PDKV, Akola during kharif season 2019-20. There were eight treatments including control and each treatment was replicated thrice in a Randomized Block Design (RBD). The results revealed that treatment Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05% was found most effective for the control of okra aphids, whiteflies, leaf hopper and shoot and fruit borer. Amongst the botanicals Neem oil 3% and NSE 5% found most effective to control of aphid population, while Neem oil 3% and 2% found most effective for management of leafhopper and whitefly. Neem oil 3%, 2% and NSE 5% are most effective to reduce the shoot and fruit borer infestation

Key Words: Botanicals, Okra, sucking pests and Shoot and fruit borer

Introduction:

Okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench] is an annual vegetable belonging to malvaceae family. Okra is valued for its tender green fruits. It is cooked in a variety of ways and used as an ingredient in a wide variety of dishes.

In India, it is grown in an area of 5,19,000 ha with an annual production of 62,71,000 metric tons. In Maharashtra area under okra cultivation is 13,982 hectare and production 1,39,401 tons (Anonymous, 2019-20). Among various reasons for low productivity the damages due to the insect pest is major one.

As high as 72 species of insects have been recorded on okra (Srinivas and Rajendran, 2003), among them fruit borers like *Earias spp.* and *Helicoverpa armigera* cause significant damage to crop to the tune of 91.60 per cent (Pareek and Bhargava, 2003).

Among sucking insect pests, aphids and leaf hoppers are important pest in the early stage of the crop which suck the plant sap, make them weak and reduce the yield. Failure to control them in the initial stage was reported to cause in yield loss to the tune of 54.04 Per cent (Chaudhary and Dadech, 1989). Whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) also suck cell sap and secretes honey dew on the leaves resulting the colonization by mold and also reduces photosynthetic ability of the crop. Resulted in stunted growth. It also transmits yellow vein mosaic virus and okra leaf curl virus.

Attempts to control the pests by insecticides generally results in resistance, secondary outbreak, phytotoxicity, toxicity to beneficial organisms and residues in food which cause health hazards to the consumers. Hence research workers have started searching out the effective, environmentally safe, eco-friendly and bio-intensive management tactics which may keep pest below ETL.

Although use of insecticides cannot be altogether omitted as they form the main stay of pest management strategies, yet their role can indubitably be limited by utilizing safer techniques of pest management such as biopesticides (plant derivatives and microbial insecticides), growing of pest tolerant/ resistant varieties and utilizing bio agents in an eco-friendly integrated pest management package.

Material And Methods

The experiment was carried out on the research field Dr. PDKV, Akola during kharif season 2019-20.

During the experimentation, in all four spraying were undertaken at an interval of 10 days commencing from 23 DAG (Days after germination) consisting of eight treatments with three replications in Randomized Block Design (RBD). The treatments consisted of spraying of botanicals at different doses and insecticides viz. (T1) Neem oil 2% @ 20 ml/L, (T2) Neem oil 3% @ 30 ml/L, (T3) NSE (Neem Seed Extract) 5%, (T4) NLE (Neem Leaf Extract) 10%, (T5) Karanj oil 1% @ 10 ml/L, (T6) Garlic Bulb Extract 3%, (T7) Quinalphos 0.05% 1ml/L including (T10) control (untreated). Variety taken AKOV-118 with plot size Gross : 4.2 x 3.0 m², Net : 3.0 x 2.1m² with spacing 60X45cm.

Pretreatment observation on sucking pests viz. aphid, leafhopper and whiteflies were taken 24 hrs. before spray from randomly selected 5 plants. Post treatment observations were recorded at 3, 7 and 10 days after each spray.

For shoot and fruit borer damage, number of healthy and damaged fruits due to borer were recorded at 3, 5 and 7 days after each spray in plot. At the time of every picking damaged fruit and healthy fruit were counted on number and weight basis to workout percent infestation of shoot and fruit borer. Total yield of okra/ha was computed on the basis of net plot yield of each treatment.

Results And Discussion**Cumulative effect of botanicals (three sprays) on aphids, leafhoppers and whiteflies**

The average population of aphid in various treatments was significantly lower i.e. 3.11 to 5.89 aphids/leaf over untreated control 9.94 aphids/leaf. Lowest count 3.11 aphids/leaf was noticed in treatment T7 (Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05%) and it was at par with T2 (Neem oil 3%) 4.60 aphids/leaf (Table 1)

The next effective treatment T3 (NSE 5%) 4.82 aphids/leaf and it was at par with rest of the treatments except control. These are in sequence T1 (Neem oil 2%) 4.91 aphids/leaf, T5 (karanj oil 1%) 5.59 aphids/leaf, T4 (Neem leaf extract 10%) 5.77 aphids/leaf and T6 (Garlic bulb extract 3%) 5.89 aphids/leaf.

Similar result was obtained by Adilakshmi *et al.* (2018) reported that NSE 5% and Neem oil were considered the most effective treatment among the botanicals against aphid population in first spray (2.97 and 3.34 aphids/leaf) and in second spray (2.71 and 3.11 aphids/leaf).

Leafhopper

The lowest population 2.80 leafhopper/leaf was recorded in treatment T7 (Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05%) and it was at par with T2 (Neem oil 3%) 3.83 leafhopper/leaf, T1 (Neem oil 2%) 4.22 leafhopper/leaf and T3 (NSE 5%) 4.27 leafhopper/leaf.

The next minimum population observed in T5 (karanj oil 1%) 4.87 leafhopper/leaf and followed by T4 (Neem leaf extract 10%) 5.34 leafhopper/leaf and T6 (Garlic bulb extract 3%) 5.60 leafhopper/leaf, all these treatments was at par with each other.

Similar result was obtained by Alam *et al.* (2010) who reported the Neem oil 3% and karanj oil 1% were considered the most effective treatment against leafhopper and providing maximum protection.

Whitefly

Average populations of whitefly in all treated plots were significantly lower 0.54 to 1.39 whitefly/leaf than the untreated control plot 1.99 whitefly/leaf. The lowest population 0.54 whitefly/leaf was recorded in treatment T7 (Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05%) and it was at par with T2 (Neem oil 3%) 0.83 whitefly/leaf, T1 (Neem oil 2%) 0.90 whitefly/leaf and T3 (NSE 5%) 0.92 whitefly/leaf

Similar result was obtained by Adilakshmi *et al.* (2018) reported the NSE 5% and Neem oil were considered the most effective treatment among the botanicals against whitefly population in first spray (1.47

and 1.60 whitefly/leaf) and in second spray (1.16 and 1.28 whitefly/leaf).

Table 1: Cumulative effect of botanicals (three sprays) on aphids, leafhoppers and whiteflies

Sr. No.	Treatment details	Cumulative Mean (three sprays)		
		Aphid/leaf	leafhopper/leaf	Whitefly/leaf
T1	Neem oil 2 %	4.91 (2.21)	4.22 (2.05)	0.90 (0.95)
T2	Neem oil 3 %	4.60 (2.14)	3.83 (1.96)	0.83 (0.91)
T3	NSE 5 %	4.82 (2.19)	4.27 (2.07)	0.92 (0.96)
T4	NLE 10 %	5.77 (2.40)	5.34 (2.31)	1.26 (1.12)
T5	Karanj oil 1 %	5.59 (2.36)	4.87 (2.21)	1.20 (1.10)
T6	Garlic bulb extract 3 %	5.89 (2.42)	5.60 (2.37)	1.39 (1.18)
T7	Quinalphos 0.05 %	3.11 (1.76)	2.80 (1.67)	0.54 (0.73)
T8	Control	9.94 (3.15)	8.88 (2.98)	1.99 (1.41)
	F test	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
	SE (m) ±	0.13	0.13	0.08
	CD at 5%	0.42	0.40	0.24
	CV (%)	10.72	11.52	13.29

(Figures in parenthesis are square root transformed values)

Cumulative mean effect of different insecticides against per cent fruit damage due to shoot and fruit borer on okra. (Table 2)

Number basis

Cumulative effect of botanical insecticides after second, third and fourth sprays presented in Table 2 revealed that, treatment T7 (Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05%) was the most promising treatment with least fruit borer infestation 7.59%. Second most effective treatments were T2 (Neem oil 3%) 13.36 % and it was at par with rest of the treatments except T4 (Neem leaf extract 10%) and T8 (control). This treatment was followed by T1 (Neem oil 2%) 14.96%, T3 (NSE 5%) 15.04%, T5 (karanj oil 1%) 17.16% and T6 (Garlic bulb extract 3%) 18.48%. The highest 28.81 per cent of fruit infestation recorded in the treatment T8 (untreated control).

On comparative analysis of different botanical insecticidal treatments, Quinalphos found to be the most effective treatment. It was followed by Neem oil 3%, Neem oil 2% and NSE 5%.

Similar trend was observed in case of per cent fruit infestation on weight basis.

The effectiveness of the botanicals observed in investigation is in conformity with Chorage *et al.* (2012) using NSE 5% which was recorded the fruit infestation on number basis 16.92% and on weight basis 17.07%.

Similar result was obtained by Subbareddy *et al.* (2018) tested different botanicals. Neem oil 0.3% found to be promising botanical insecticide with minimum fruit infestation 13.53% on number basis and 13.38% on weight basis and NSE 5% recorded fruit infestation on number basis 14.31% and on weight basis 14.20%.

Also, Pachole *et al.* (2017) reported that, Neem oil 3% recorded 12.99%, NSE 5% 15.24% and Neem leaf extract 5% 17.94% fruit infestation which support our findings.

Effect of different insecticidal treatments on fruit yield of okra.

Highest yield of okra fruits 50.53 q/ha was obtained in treatment T7 (Quinalphos 25 EC @ 0.05%) and it was at par with rest of the treatments except T4 (Neem leaf extract 10%) and T8 (untreated control) followed by T2 (Neem oil 3%) 47.62 q/ha, T1 (Neem oil 2%) 45.60 q/ha, T3 (NSE 5%) 43.28 q/ha, T5 (karanj oil 1%) 40.42 q/ha. and T6 (Garlic bulb extract 3%) 37.56 q/ha. The next highest yield recorded in T4 (Neem leaf extract 10 %) 34.17q/ha. The lowest fruit yield was recorded in the T8 (control) 23.27 q/ha. (Table 2)

The above yield parameters are in line with Adilakshmi *et al.* (2018) who observed that NSE 5% prove to be more effective against sucking pest infestation in okra and relatively more yield 83.27q/ha. Singh *et al.* (2015) reported highest marketable fruit yield of the treatment quinalphos 25EC @0.05% (62.26 q/ha).

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Table 2: Cumulative effect of botanicals on per cent fruit damage by shoot and fruit borer on okra

Sr. No.	Treatment details	Per cent fruit damage by shoot and fruit borer (cumulative mean of four sprays)		Yield Q/ha
		Number basis	Weight basis	
T1	Neem oil 2 %	14.96 (22.75)	14.62 (22.48)	45.60
T2	Neem oil 3 %	13.36 (21.43)	13.22 (21.32)	47.62
T3	NSE 5 %	15.04 (22.81)	15.14 (22.89)	43.28
T4	NLE 10 %	19.25 (26.02)	19.20 (25.98)	34.17
T5	Karanj oil 1 %	17.16 (24.47)	16.85 (24.23)	40.42
T6	Garlic bulb extract 3 %	18.48 (25.46)	18.57 (25.52)	37.56
T7	Quinalphos 0.05 %	7.59 (15.99)	7.29 (15.66)	50.53
T8	Control	28.81 (32.46)	29.37 (32.81)	23.27
	F test	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
	SE (m) ±	1.45	1.48	5.00
	CD at 5%	4.40	4.48	15.18
	CV (%)	10.63	10.81	21.51

(Figure in parenthesis are arc sine transformed values)